

ISA ENVIRONMENTAL REPORTING TEMPLATES AND DATA REPOSITORY: INSIGHTS FROM THE ATLAS PROJECT

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Contents

1. Objectives.....	3
2. Executive summary.....	3
3. Draft evaluation on the existing data reporting templates	4
4. Recommendations on the ISA environmental data repository	5
5. Recommendations for data collection.....	9
6. Recommendations for video data collection and processing	10
7. Conclusions	11
8. Acknowledgements	12
9. References.....	12
10. Figures and Tables	14

1. Objectives

Evaluate the common grounds for standardization of the International Seabed Authority's (ISA) environmental data and those generated by the European Union Horizon 2020 project ATLAS (grant agreement 678760). Special emphasis was given to generate recommendations on database structure and developments, video data collection and processing as well as to produce a draft evaluation of the existing ISA's data reporting templates. We hope that this project will foster the collaboration between ISA and ATLAS in the near future.

2. Executive summary

1. Environmental data are essential to understand and monitor the effects of deep-sea mining in the Area. Appropriate guidelines on data collection, storage and reporting facilitate the translation of environmental data into meaningful information for decision making.
2. Environmental data collected using standardized sampling protocols become easier to manage and transfer. Although the development of such standards over large areas of the deep-sea is a challenging task, efforts in this direction would be beneficial.
3. Reporting and storage schemes should capture the complexity and variety of environmental data. Flexible reporting and storage schemes may represent a better alternative than the actual generalised reporting templates.
4. Regardless of the reporting scheme, metadata about origin, spatial and temporal coverage, protocols, gears, sample types and quality have always to complement any type of environmental data.
5. External organizations, projects and databases may provide important hints and resources in building the ISA environmental data repository and in structuring data collection, storage and reporting processes. Cooperation is of paramount importance.
6. Data collection, data management and governance are all interrelated aspects that need to be considered at the same time in order to avoid a disarticulation between data accumulation, knowledge production and compliance with regulations.

7. In order to increase the utility of imagery data, future efforts should consider four aspects: appropriate spatial and temporal planning of video collection, automated image processing tools, standard practices in image annotations and regional image-base species catalogues providing permanent references for future studies.

3. Draft evaluation on the existing data reporting templates

Environmental data relevant in the context of deep-sea mining comprise heterogeneous data sources and types. Biodiversity alone requires measurements of an array of variables at genetic, population, community and ecosystem levels appropriately scaled both geographically and temporally. The questions being asked, the instruments used and the protocols adopted will generate diversified records and attributes. In our opinion, the flattening of such a variety of data types into two-dimensional reporting templates does not match the complexity of environmental data management. On the one hand, tables created to accommodate a large variety of data types will be overcomplicated by a high number of fields specific to certain data groups, but meaningless for the remaining ones resulting in a cluttered reporting process. On the other hand, generalized reporting templates could not be able to capture all the important aspects of each group of data, resulting either in Contractors forced to use individual solutions or in data losses.

We believe that both ISA repository and reporting process should be based on a pool of related tables organized in a hierarchical scheme. At each level of the hierarchy, Contractors should answer specific questions necessary to track metadata and actual data by choosing the tables that better represent their types and sources (Section 3 and Fig. 1 and 2).

We would like to emphasise that data collection, data management and governance are all interrelated aspects that need to be considered at the same time in order to avoid a disarticulation between data accumulation, knowledge production and compliance with regulations. As governance set questions and objectives, iterative efforts should try to *i)* define meaningful scales to meet those objectives, *ii)* identify what environmental variables have to be measured, *iii)* standardize sampling gears and protocols used to collect measures of the relevant variables as well as digital

processes to store and transmit data, and *iv*) include the use of standardized sampling gears and protocols in regulations. This process, by specifying the data collection strategy, would enormously facilitate the data reporting and management processes. Moreover, it would allow for a rapid and objective assessment of data completeness and quality.

4. Recommendations on the ISA environmental data repository

1. Different organizations have produced or are working on international guidelines for data collection. ISA should look to follow these guidelines and *develop a database system that is standardized and that could talk to external data sources* (e.g., GBIF, GOOS and GOOS BioEco, MBON, GEOBON, WoRMS, OBIS, EMODNET).
2. From our perspective, it will be difficult to build a single template for Environmental data in general and “Pelagic and Benthic Biological Samples” in particular, that contain relevant information for all ecosystem compartments. Therefore, *we suggest building a database composed of multiple linked tables organized at different levels by sampling methods* or different types of habitats/ecosystems.
3. We suggest *structuring the environmental data on four interrelated levels*; the first three levels comprising metadata explaining origin (Level 1 – Data Reference), spatial and temporal distribution (Level 2 – Sampling Stations) and typology (Level 3 – Samples) of the data reported; the fourth level should include the actual data obtained in individual samplings and finer spatial and temporal referencing where needed. The reporting process should consist of at least one table for each level.
4. We envision a flexible reporting scheme, where, *at each level, a defined set of reporting tables is designed to accommodate the specificity of the data being transmitted* while respecting the information that should be carried at each level (i.e., origin, spatial and temporal distribution, typology and actual data).
5. However, *we acknowledge that generalised reporting templates could represent a viable possibility for metadata* (Level 1 – 3) even if some of the flexibility proposed in the following scheme would have to be forfeited.

6. Level 1 – Data Reference should provide information on how data were produced (Table 1). Actual reporting templates accommodate cruise metadata, i.e. *in situ* measurements. Future developments of the database could also take into account *ex situ* measurements as derived from models or remote sensing or *in situ* data already available in global repositories (e.g., GBIF, OBIS, PANGEA, EMODNET, SeaLifeBase). *We believe it would be valuable to acknowledge the existence of ex situ and additional in situ data in the ISA repository* (Levels 1 to 3).
7. Level 2 – Sampling Stations should provide information on where and when the data were produced (Table 2). Traditionally, sampling stations assume “point” shapes defined by latitude-longitude coordinate pairs. However, “polygon” shapes could more easily describe dense sampling effort such as multibeam data and derived topographic maps; finally, “transect” shapes could better represent semi-continuous 3D profiles of the water column over geographic ranges. *Contractors should be able to choose the shape that better represents their data type and sampling design.*
8. Level 3 – Samples should contain information on the gears and protocol used to collect individual samples; it should also provide summarizing information such as total biomass or number of specimens collected (Table 3). Additionally *we suggest developing a preliminary assessment of the quality of the samples included in the database at level 3.* Such assessments tend to be really data specific; e.g., CTD and multibeam data depend on accurate and frequent calibrations of the instruments; video data outputs depend, among other things, on accurate and synchronized navigation data that allow to correctly geo-reference biological observations and other environmental measures. Quality index could become more accurate as new standardized sampling methodology are developed and accepted.
9. *At present, contractors should self-evaluate the quality of their data based on general criteria proposed by the ISA* (e.g., completeness of taxonomic identification, instrument calibration, precision and estimates of error margins of instruments used, etc.). This could probably start in cooperation with the ATLAS project for some specific gears.
10. Level 4 - Actual data should provide the data collected during each sample, either unprocessed or processed (Table 4). We believe that the structure of most

data can be approximate by five data types, each in association with different sampling methods (Fig. 2):

- i. **Profiles** – describe biological or oceanographic properties of the water column (e.g., CTD casts, stratified eDNA sampling);
 - ii. **Transects** – continuous record on the seabed of biological, geological or oceanographic variables along a linear path (e.g., video records, trawls);
 - iii. **Points** – one or more measurements at a single location on the seafloor (e.g., multicores, baited cameras);
 - iv. **Time-series** – set of data points collected at the same locations on the seafloor at regular or semi-regular intervals of time following consistent and comparable protocols (e.g., moorings, colonization of artificial structures);
 - v. **Areas** – environmental data structured in spatial grids (raster) or polygons describing one or more variables over an area; they usually are the result of interpolation, syntheses or remote sensing (e.g., seafloor topography, model outputs, satellite measures).
11. We believe that the reporting of actual data (level 4) should use **multiple reporting templates reflecting the structure of the different data types rather than a single reporting template**. This approach would help standardize the way contractors report environmental data by limiting the adoption of individual solutions in cases of mismatch between real data and template structure (e.g., CTD casts consist of lists of observation that cannot be properly reported in the single cell provided by the actual reporting template).
12. Note that even if all actual data are related to individual sampling stations appropriately geo-referenced, **finer spatial and temporal referencing may be needed at level 4**. This is the case for transect and time-series data, where each observation has to be associated with latitude/longitude pairs and time annotations, respectively. Reporting templates have to meet these requirements.
13. We recommend **defining a contact person at all the appropriate levels of the reporting process**.
14. We strongly recommend associating taxonomic data to the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) via the AphiaID. Their web-service allows

automation of this process and, among other things, to get the full classification for any taxon and to resolve unaccepted names to accepted ones. *Contractors should then only need to report the lower taxonomic rank at which they identify their specimens.* In addition, every taxonomic group will be associated with the metadata available in WoRMS (range, images, biology, etc.) and to any future development of their repository (ecological-traits).

15. The list of *specimens collected for taxonomic, histologic or genetic studies should always be a stand-alone sample.* It would be important to note how the specimens are preserved. As required by the actual reporting templates, genetic sequences should be deposited in public repository (e.g., GENE BANK).
16. It would then be ideal to *send the collected data to experts in different subjects or taxonomic groups for their review.* This could probably start in cooperation with the ATLAS project since it contains multidisciplinary expertise and could provide inputs for developing data quality standards.
17. In future, it will be important to *standardize measurements, sampling gears and protocols.* This will provide both a solid base to assess quality and completeness of the data provided by the contractors and a more structured and robust way of collecting, storing and comparing environmental data.
18. It is equally important to *standardize digital protocols and vocabulary in order to facilitate data searching, collection and sharing.* This process consist of multiple steps: define the vocabulary used in descriptions of data; specify file types for different data types; authorship and citation suggestions, possibly based on unique identifiers such as DOIs. Useful international standards and conventions we suggest to consult:
 - i. *ISO 19115 and 19139* provide the basic principles and the overall requirements for standardization of geographic information as well as an XML Schema implementation of such requirements;
 - ii. *The conventions for CF (Climate and Forecast)* attempts to propose a clear, adequate and flexible definition of the metadata needed for climate and forecast data. Their ideas may have a wider application.
19. If ISA will adopt the suggestions listed in the above points then *we would recommend using the same templates for all mineral resources* since the tables

would be ready to receive any kind of information. Tables on level 1 could flag the target mineral resource of each cruise.

5. Recommendations for data collection

1. Data collection during all phases of mining process (as described in the Mining Code, including prospecting, exploration and exploitation) should be designed to address existing regulations and recommendations, to fill knowledge gaps relevant to those regulations, and to facilitate measurements of agreed criteria, indicators and thresholds.
2. Based on such regulation sets of environmental variables able to capture relevant structures and processes should be identified in order to properly meet governance objectives and standardize collection efforts. The Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) has defined a set of *essential ocean variables* (both physical and biogeochemical) that should guide ocean observations at a global level based on relevance, feasibility and cost effectiveness. This information could be relevant to define within the ISA reporting scheme standardized observation protocols that would ease the translation of data into useful information.
3. The Group on Earth Observations Biodiversity Observation Network (GEO BON) is working on a similar project that is trying to define *essential biodiversity variables*. The aim is to improve the acquisition, coordination and delivery of biodiversity observations from different sources. The project is ongoing, but it is expected to provide tools for monitoring and managing biodiversity change over different scales and at genetic, species, community and ecosystem levels. Its outcome could represent a valuable resource for the ISA.
4. Regular assessments should evaluate overall geographic coverage, observation effort and temporal coverage of the available observations. Appropriate actions should address identified gaps and biases.

6. Recommendations for video data collection and processing

1. The volume of video data and the velocity at which new videos are produced pose serious concerns when compared with our current capacity to process and digest these data into valuable information. *Automated approaches could help annotation processes at two phases: image pre-processing and actual annotation.* We believe that image pre-processing is at a more developed state. Efforts have been made to: assess video quality (Pirenne et al. 2015); enhance image quality (Schoening et al. 2012); estimate areas (Dias et al. 2015). Automatic recognition of megafauna and seafloor substrates is a non-trivial task but substantial efforts have been made to: classify automatically seabed substrates (Pugh et al. 2014); identify and quantify of keystone species (Purser et al. 2009); map habitats (MIDAS 2015).
2. It is important to *standardize the way biological and ecological information is extracted from video data.* Schoening (et al. 2016) provide an extensive review of the available computational and manual annotation approaches.
3. We suggest developing *automatic ways of extracting frames associated with biological annotations.* Senior taxonomists could then help to identify species and misclassification errors.
4. The utility of video data drops dramatically when navigation files are not correctly associated. *We recommend all video provided to ISA to have a date and a latitude-longitude stamp.*
5. *Substrate should be considered as a continuous variable,* i.e. the substrate is assumed to remain constant until a new annotation is taken.
6. *Develop standard methods for abundance estimation.* Possible alternatives are abundance estimates based on video frames randomly extracted from different substrate types and standardized by depth; abundance estimates based on linear distance (individuals/m or individuals/m²) on segments of videos randomly chosen within different substrate types and standardized by depth.
7. Many species in the deep-sea are difficult to identify using imagery tools without the help of expert taxonomists and detailed analyses of collected specimens. This is especially relevant for deep-sea invertebrates such as sponges and cold-water corals. Adding to the limitations of imagery tools for

species identification is the fact that many species in the deep-sea are poorly described or are new to science and therefore still to be described. *Regional image-based guides for species identification and metrics to determine the confidence of the identification should improve the output of video annotations.* Howell and Davies (2010) provide an example of deep-sea species image catalogue used for video data.

8. In particular, *regional image-based species catalogues provide permanent references for future studies* that grant: i) consistency in identification; ii) detection and correction of misidentified taxa; iii) structured use of morphospecies and Operational Taxonomic Unit in video analysis when identification at genus or species level is not possible.
9. *Physical specimens should ground-truth regional image-based species catalogues, species-distribution models and habitat classification schemes.* In the absence of sample-based species identification particular care should be placed in consulting expert taxonomists and in conducting image analysis that emphasize both morphological differences among organisms and the way they interact with their *milieu*.
10. The questions we aim at answering using video data should *define the spatial and temporal scales at which videos are collected and how they are collected* (e.g. linear transects, target specific habitats, etc.). Even though extensive sampling designs have high associated costs, it is important to attempt defining scientific guidelines for video collection (e.g., Buhl-Mortensen et al. 2015; Durden et al. 2016).

7. Conclusions

Environmental data are essential to understand and monitor the effects of deep-sea mining in the Area. However, data by themselves have little significance. They need structure and context in order to provide useful information. Information that once compiled and combined can produce knowledge able to guide governance decisions.

Adequate reporting and storing schemes can facilitate the translation of environmental data into knowledge. The reporting process have to ensure that both data and data context (metadata) get to destination. Given the complexity of environmental data, we propose adopting flexible reporting schemes able to minimize

data losses during the reporting process. At the same time, the ISA data repository should facilitate the digestion of environmental data into information by structuring data from different sources at appropriate scales and contexts. The main challenge is to store in a viable way a large array of data types and formats. Again, we believe that a flexible repository structured at multiple hierarchical levels can better face this challenge. Furthermore, such a repository should receive and transmit inputs from external resources promoting the conversion of information into knowledge.

Finally, it is important to remark that the capacity of environmental data to address existing regulations and recommendations depends on the definition of appropriate scales and standards for data collection. Moreover, a well-delineated data collection strategy would enormously facilitate and improve both data reporting and data management. Several working groups, projects and organizations are working directly or indirectly on the ambitious task of defining scales and standards for environmental data in the deep-sea. We believe that cooperation is the key to sound and useful data management policies.

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10. Figures and Tables

Figure 1 – Proposed structure of the ISA data repository.

ISA ENVIRONMENTAL DATA: *collection and storage*

Figure 2 – Schematic view of the different types of environmental data

LEVEL 1 – DATA REFERENCE

Table for CRUISES

Table for MODELS**

Table for OTHER IN/EX SITU DATA**

FIELDS	DEFINITION	FIELDS	DEFINITION	FIELDS	DEFINITION
Cruise Name	Cruise, expedition	Model Name*		Dataset Name*	
Research Vessel	name	Category*	NOMADS categories**	Spatial Information*	Global/Regional/ Local
Leg Number	number of leg	Spatial Information*	Global/Regional/Local	Resolution*	1/12°, 1/8°, etc.
Geographical Area	Pacific Ocean, etc.	Resolution*	1/12°, 1/8°, etc.	Geographical Area	Pacific Ocean, etc.
Area sector	CCZ, etc.	Geographical Area	Pacific Ocean, etc.	Period of Record (St)*	
Start Date*	Cruise Start	Period of Record (St)*		Period of Record (End)*	
End Date*	Cruise End	Period of Record (End)*		Area sector	CCZ, etc.
Contact*		Area sector	CCZ, etc.	Description*	Brief model description
		Description*	Brief model description	Output format*	Type of outputs produced
		Output format*	Type of outputs produced	Contact*	
		Contact*			

Table 1 – Example of data reference reporting tables (Level 1); *fields not present in the original reporting tables; **adapted from NOAA Operational Model Archive and Distribution System (NOMADS) project.

LEVEL 2 – SAMPLING STATIONS

FIELDS	DEFINITION
Station ID	Unique station Identifier
Date	yyyy-mm-dd
Type*	Point/Transect/Area
Sampling start time	hh:mm:ss
Sampling start depth	maximun bottom depth [m]
Sampling start latitude	decimal deg (instrument at seafloor)
Sampling start longitude	decimal deg (instrument at seafloor)
Sampling end time	hh:mm:ss
Sampling end depth	maximun bottom depth [m]
Sampling end latitude	decimal deg (instrument at seafloor)
Sampling end longitude	decimal deg (instrument at seafloor)
Exploration Block ID	Exploration block identifier
Hydrothermal activity*	Presence of hydrothermal activity
Remarks/Comments	

Table 2 – Example of sampling stations reporting table (Level 2);

*fields not present in the original reporting tables.

NOTE:

Coordinates should be held in a relational table:

- Some stations may be specified by one pair of coordinates (**Point Stations**);
- Some stations may be specified by two pairs of coordinates (**Transect Stations**);
- Some stations may be specified by multiple pairs of coordinates (**Area Stations**).

LEVEL 3 – SAMPLES

Fields	Definition
Sample ID	Unique Sample Identified
Sampling Gear**	Ideally should refer to a set of predefined sampling gears.
Sample Type	Biology Oceanography Geology
Data Type*	Point Transect Raster Time Series
Habitat	Water column Chimney Crust Sediment Bottom*
Location of samples	Storage location on land
Collection Code	
Institution Storing Code	
Habitat Description	Rock Sediment Steep slope Flat Etc.
Sampling Protocol**	Protocol for handling and sampling. Ideally should refer to a set of predefined protocols.
Area or Volume sampled	m ² or l, respectively
Summarizing Fields*,**	Should be sample specific and stored in a related table (e.g. # specimens collected, avg. temperature, crust coverage, morphological taxonomists, etc.)
Sample Quality*,**	Sample quality assessed based on sets of criteria defined within the ISA
Contact details	

NOTE:

Samples collected with *different gears* or referring to *different sample or data types* should represent individual entries in the database and be associate to unique sample IDs.

Tabella 3 – Example of samples reporting table (Level 3); *fields not present in the original reporting tables; **fields that should refer to related tables.

LEVEL 4 – ACTUAL DATA: COLLECTED SPECIMENS

Fields	Definition
Actual Value ID*	Unique Value Identified
Latitude	
Longitude	
Depth	
AphiaID*	AphiaID of the lowest taxonomic rank at which the specimen has been identified
Taxon Name	Report the name of the lower identified taxa (species, genus, etc.)
Taxonomic Resolution*	Species, genus, etc.
Morphospecies*	Morphospecies tag if assigned
Taxon density	benthic (ind/m ²); pelagic (ind/m ³)
Relative abundance (%)	
Relative dominance (%)	
Preservation*	EtOH 60%; EtOH96%; F 10%; etc.
Voucher specimen code	
Genebank, sequence number etc.	
Specimen Sex	
Specimen Weight	
Reproductive state	
Life Stage	
Notes	
Tissue Descriptor	
Associated Taxa (Actual Value ID)	
Associated Specimens (Comments)	

NOTE 1:

Point data (as in this example) do not require to repeat latitude, longitude and depth for each entry; *Transect data* require to repeat latitude, longitude and depth for each entry; *Time series data* require to specify date and time for each entry.

NOTE 2:

Ideally different actual data table should be provided for the different types and formats of collected data.

Tabella 4 – Example of actual data reporting table (Level 4); *fields not present in the original reporting tables; several reporting table should be created to accommodate different types and formats of actual data.

